

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE FAMILY IN FORMING A SENSE OF NATIONAL PRIDE IN SCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH FOLKORAL CREATION

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Summary. *The rich spiritual and cultural heritage of our people, the future of the country and nation determines the future of the country in the process of spiritual and educational work, which is regularly organized in preschool educational institutions.*

Keywords: *Innovation, pedagogical process, means of demonstration, national identity, national pride.*

Anotasiya. *Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida va oilada muntazam olib boriladigan, tarbiyalanuvchilarni Vatanga sadoqat, milliy g'urur va buyuk ajdodlar ma'naviy merosiga hurmat ruhida tarbiyalashga qaratilgan ma'naviy-ma'rifiy, tarbiyaviy ishlar jarayonida xalqimizning boy ma'naviy-madaniy merosi, sharqonq va umumbashariy qadriyatlar asosida mamlakat, millat kelajagini belgilaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Yangilik, pedagogik jarayon, ko'rsatish vositalari, milliy o'zlik, milliy g'urur.*

Резюме. *Богатое духовное и культурное наследие нашего народа, будущее страны и нации определяет будущее страны в процессе духовно-просветительской работы, которая регулярно организуется в дошкольных образовательных учреждениях.*

Ключевые слова: *Инновация, педагогический процесс, средства демонстрации, национальное самосознание, национальная гордость.*

Pride in children of preschool age, it is important to study the current state of not only preschool education organizations, but also the family. Because children's free time is mostly spent at home, in the family circle. It would be a mistake not to

take this into account, if we do not think more deeply about the duties and tasks of parents in the upbringing of the young generation .

One of the aspects of national pride is to serve the country, the nation, and the country with loyalty. There can be no word about the perfection of a person who does not love his country, who is indifferent to the history and fate of his nation .

A constant influencing force in family education is the relationship in the family, the family environment, the interaction of family members , the behavior of parents, siblings and others, the cultural and political level, the culture of behavior, the family's income, living conditions, and other factors. circumstances are the main factors affecting the child's development. The more orderly, well-behaved the family is, and the more sincere the relations between its members are , the more effective family upbringing will be.

The formation of national pride and patriotism is the duty of every parent, educator and public to the Motherland. Therefore , it is appropriate to carry out national pride and ideological education work with the parents of children of pre-school educational organizations.

Therefore, formation of a sense of self-sacrifice for the fate of the nation and the country in the children of preschool educational organizations from a young age has an important place in ideological education. For this, from the first years of a child's life, it is necessary to use the forms of introducing him to the world of things, specific to our national traditions. Because the future of the state and society largely depends on how the young generation grows up . In turn, national pride is determined by the moral level of the nation.

It is the duty of all of us to educate the young generation from their childhood with positive feelings such as national pride , love and respect for people, appreciation and respect for the motherland.

The importance of the family in the life of the society has been emphasized by the Uzbek people since ancient times.

In the holy book of Zoroastrianism "Avesta" special emphasis is placed on issues of family education. This work reflects the ideas of protecting the family,

rewarding women who have given birth to and raised several children, and assigning them an allowance.

In Islamic values, special importance is attached to raising a child in the family as a person worthy of the society, as a moral, hardworking, good person. In particular, in the hadith " A father cannot leave more inheritance to his child than morals", it is said that the most important aspect of family education is to give children morals.

contain information about the mothers of famous people, their wisdom and intelligence, and their use of folk oral creativity in raising children . For example, in Ibn Arabshah's work "Amir Temur", there are examples of the role of Amir Temur's wife Saraymulkhanim (Bibikhanim) in state affairs and in raising children. Abu Ali ibn Sina's work "Tadbiri Manzil" is devoted to the problems of family education. Valuable opinions were expressed in it about folklore and its importance in child education .

is not inherently moral or immoral . People are not actually born with ready-made personal qualities, habits and skills . Such characteristics are gradually formed in their social life under the influence of personal and other experiences, traditions of ancestors, and education. It is better to start raising children early. In the process of education, it is necessary to inculcate good positive habits in them, to try to carefully notice their passions and interests.

the child's development into a perfect human being and the resulting mental and physiological conditions are considered. It is noted that a child brought up by means of examples of folk oral works will grow up to be resilient, courageous, brave and hardworking.

Ibn Sina pays special attention to the role of the father in family education. In his opinion, the head of the family should educate the family members and start them on the right path.

In general, Eastern thinkers emphasize the need to pay special attention to factors such as family, family environment, and heredity in the education of a well-

rounded person, and at the same time, they highly appreciate the educational importance of folk oral creativity.

pays attention to the maintenance of affection between parents and children . In this, the father makes good use of the wisdom of the people while admonishing his son. It is recommended to take a reasonable approach to child education, to make good use of folk wisdom, to refrain from cursing and fighting even when one is dissatisfied with the child, and to ask for help from teachers in this area.

From this point of view, it is necessary to pay special attention to raising children in the family based on examples of folk oral creativity . In this, the role of grandparents is especially important.

folk oral creativity include the following sources: national customs, traditions, folk games, religious teachings, folk art, music, song, dance, etc. .

folk oral works, introduce the child to happy feelings from the first age. The boy "travels" to faraway places together with the heroes of the fairy tale. They get to know life there. A fairy tale sharpens his mind, enriches his thinking, and develops his ability to imagine. The fluent, figurative language style of the story told in the family develops the child's speech. Bright, lifelike images deeply affect his emotions . He meets intelligent, light- hearted, positive heroes, who grieve when disaster strikes, rejoice when they win, and punish evil and greedy people. The reliable moral ideas of the fairy tale told by adults in the family encourage the child to think, compare his behavior with the behavior of his favorite fairy tale heroes, in the image of the heroes, children learn to be fearless and truthful. They gradually acquire such qualities as setting specific goals, working to achieve them, overcoming various obstacles, making friends, and being loyal to their comrades .

Children listen to stories told by adults in the family with interest. The fairy tale must be appropriate for the child's age . It is necessary to read the fairy tale slowly, without haste, expressively, to visualize the image of the characters before the child's eyes.

the child, parents should also watch the pictures with the plot drawn according to the fairy tale, and interpret them. Asking the child not so complicated questions ,

encouraging him to retell a story or a picture is very useful in terms of practical pedagogy. It develops the child's memory and attention and teaches him to be conscious of what he does . The life experience of the child is very little during this period . In his eyes, the fairy tale and the real world are completely different. Was the boy "really a witchy old woman, a giant, a flying carpet ? " asks questions like At such a time, parents should carefully explain the connection and differences between fairy tales and material existence. Otherwise, his ability to hypothesize is impaired. He begins to look at fairy tales with distrust. As a result, his interest in them fades. For example, it is necessary to carefully explain that instead of flying carpets, science and technology were invented, and as a result of the development of the era, airplanes were invented, and television instead of a glass globe. As the child grows up , he better understands the connection between the fairy tale and the real world and learns more deeply the moral and aesthetic views of them.

why fairy tales, narratives, and other stories have a strong impact on a child's worldview is the legendary, understandable interpretation of real reality in accordance with the child's age and worldview. Strong and fair people, cute animals close to the child's spiritual world appear as the heroes of folklore . In the 13th-16th centuries, in the Timurid dynasty, the children of nobles and courtiers were raised by healthy , intelligent, strong, polite, eloquent female nannies. Special attention was paid to the nanny's health , neatness and intelligence. The main task of nannies in raising children is to feed them properly , dress them neatly, take them for a walk in the fresh air, teach them morals, and tell them stories and epics. With the help of stories, fairy tales, narratives, war novels, nannies paid special attention to raising children with good morals, intelligence, promptness, and perseverance.

For this purpose, they also widely used folk proverbs, proverbs and riddles. The following educational methods used by nannies using examples of folk oral creativity were important in raising children:

an example, give advice; Formation of moral qualities such as love for the motherland, courage, pursuit of knowledge, justice, correctness, bravery, friendship,

loyalty, harmony, striving to be healthy and strong, keeping order and so on. For this purpose, they used fairy tales, narratives, stories, proverbs, and songs.

In addition, in the family, forms of logical thinking were used, such as comparing, testing, exaggerating some features, and riddles and quick speaking were used in order to develop responsiveness, eloquence, and fluent speech in children.

Various national games are also used in the formation of such qualities as dexterity, friendship, honesty, and the ability to show one's identity in children.

As the history - the witness of the centuries, proverbs, which are the reflection of the national spirit of the people, are the masterpieces that enrich the oral creativity of the people, which have been passed down from generation to generation as the words of our ancestors.

"the words of the fathers and the eye of the mind" in everyday life, in people's interactions with each other, indicates that a person has a sharp mind and insight. The influence of proverbs on the educational process is significant, inculcating the wise thoughts contained in it into the minds of children, and creating the basis for distinguishing the concepts of good and bad.

Folk proverbs are an important source in raising the spirituality of the young generation, in the development and improvement of speech culture. Folk proverbs have a special place in raising the feelings of loyalty to the Motherland, the legacy of our ancestors - national values, national traditions, and pride in the hearts of our future successors - the growing young generation.

Proverbs are recognized as an important educational tool in the historical experience of the people. They are often used in everyday life. Especially the older members of the family use proverbs appropriately when encouraging children to be good, virtuous, satisfied, neat, and hardworking. A proverb is short and concise, figurative, grammatically and logically complete, a wise phrase, a sentence with a deep meaning, which encourages the child to think independently. Teaches to express ideas clearly and concisely. It has a certain rhythmic form. Life experiences, attitude to society, history, mental state, ethical and aesthetic feelings, and positive

qualities of ancestors are embodied in proverbs. Over the centuries, it has been refined among the people, and has become a concise and poetic form.

Proverbs are extremely rich and diverse in terms of subject matter. Various proverbs were created about the homeland, work, science, friendship, harmony, wisdom, vigilance, language and speech culture, as well as negative vices. Examples of the proverbs of the Turkic peoples were first presented in the work "Devonu lug'otit turk" by Mahmud Kashgari.

A proverb is sometimes called a parable, adage, wisdom, proverb, rebuke, saying of elders, saying of sages, saying of fathers. The socio-political and educational importance of proverbs is very great. The difference between a proverb and a proverb is that in a proverb, a picture of something is given, its description, and in a proverb, a complete conclusion is expressed.

Narratives told in the family are also important in forming a sense of national pride in children. Narrative **is an** oral story that describes events and events, human activity, sometimes through fiction, sometimes realistically. The volume of the narrative is short, consists of 2 or 3 episodes, does not have a traditional methodological form. Usually, starting with a simple narrative, it is loosely interpreted in the process of passing from word of mouth to word of mouth. The narrative is based on reality and events related to a historical person. According to the ideological content, historical narration and toponymic narrations are divided. In historical narratives, events related to the activities of a person and national heroes are narrated, the ideal standards of morality and decency are promoted, and information is given about certain facts. Such narrations were also created based on the events related to the lives of Navoi, Ulughbek, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Amir Temur and others. In the toponymic narratives, the events related to the names of towns and villages, fortresses, palaces, and mausoleums, as well as the reasons for their occurrence, are told.

proper regulation of family relations and upbringing of children as perfect (honest) human beings are given a lot of space. Hadiths encourage children to respect their parents, husbands and wives to respect each other by being tolerant and

harmonious, people to be morally mature, spiritually pure and compassionate towards others. .

Chapters 1-24 of Imam Bukhari's work "Al Adab al-Mufrad", the famous Muhaddith of the Islamic world, describe issues such as the importance of honoring parents, honoring them, and the need for children to fulfill their duties perfectly.

Hadiths are an important source of education in the minds of the young generation for the formation of such qualities as honesty, goodness, kindness, justice, hard work, friendship, humility, endurance, and patience.

folk oral creativity in children are the formation of moral qualities such as correctness, truthfulness, humility, self-criticism, enthusiasm and sincerity, thoughtfulness, at the same time lying, arrogance, self-righteousness. It is important in creating a sense of struggle against vices such as self-centeredness, selfishness, and lack of concern. Also, the child's voluntary qualities such as self -sacrifice, determination, courage, and self-restraint are effectively formed through examples of folk art. Children with these qualities will be fully matured.

Modern pedagogy requires an approach with respect for the child's personality and recognition of his uniqueness as a person. One of the important aspects of this approach is to determine qualities such as self-respect, constant striving for perfection in the child, without harming the child's unique aspects. Scientists say that a child's character is mainly formed before he turns 5 years old. In later age stages, his personality gradually develops. So, how a child is formed determines the content of his future life.

Uzbek families have experience-tested methods of raising children in accordance with the national framework, which can be shown as follows: explanation, habituation, teaching, training, children's daily routine, example, request. make, beg, wish, approve, advise, exhort, exhort, praise, thank, pray, applaud, wish, comfort, cheer, ta rebuke making (blushing), threatening, slandering, warning, swearing, threatening, cursing, etc. There is no doubt that the wise use of each of these will have a good effect in raising a well-rounded person in the future.

Parents should mainly use two methods in forming a sense of national pride in children through folk oral creativity.

The first is **persuasion** - you need to do this to the child from an early age, because it is said that its implementation is necessary for one reason or another. The child is convinced of the usefulness and necessity of the work he has done in the form of heroes of fairy tales and epics. For example, ideas such as why a child should wash his hands before eating, tidying up, putting away his toys in an orderly manner, the benefits of making friends and being loyal to a friend, etc. slide films based on fairy tales are shown through images from movies.

The second is **to encourage children** to acquire positive qualities by acting under the influence of fairy-tale heroes . It is appropriate to use proverbs to encourage children to work hard, be kind, and be patient. When a child repeats a certain positive activity in an orderly and consistent manner, it becomes a habit. Habituation covers many types of activities, such as observing daily routines, including the manners of greeting, being friendly to friends, and being able to respect parents.

The signs of good manners and manners in a child are mainly determined by means of examples of folk oral creativity. Because the various characters in the play are embodied mainly in front of the child's eyes . Their behavior serves as an example for children. For example, the farmer's care for a bird with broken wings, the impoverishment of an old woman who was not satisfied with the fish she gave him, affect children very quickly. They develop hatred for greed, love for the farmer who was kind to the stork, and a sense of satisfaction .

When parents strive to form moral qualities in their children, they should effectively use the personal example of national heroes. In this, they will be helped by the heroes of fairy tales and epics . In the form of heroes of fairy tales and epics, children are taught the unity of work and words , and the honesty of their actions. Persuasion, encouragement, proof, influence, role model, etc. are important in educating children based on examples of folk oral creativity.

It is important to encourage children in raising them through examples of folk art . In this case, the important aspects of motivation are manifested in the likeness of children as positive heroes. Including "My Alpomish", "My brave boy like Gorogli sultan", "My brave son like Jalaliddi Manguberdi", "Oybarchin girl, my "swallow". As a result of such encouragement, a feeling of feeling like a national hero is formed in the child's psyche and the desire to do new things is awakened. Folk heroes act as a factor encouraging children to do good, a stimulus, and make them confident in their own strength. Parental praise, encouragement, and approval tell him that he is doing the right thing, that he has completed his task well. But it is necessary to be able to observe the norm. Fairy tales, epics, narratives should also be effectively used in the formation of orderliness, humanity, observation, diligence, patriotism, etc. in the upbringing of children in the family.

Parents should pay special attention to children's reading in the family. The majority of the family library should be occupied by folklore samples. Because such works are close to the psyche of the child . Their language is simple, fluent and popular. Instilling a love of books in a child from a young age should take a central place in the activities of parents.

up to school age with colorful, illustrated fairy tales, narratives, and stories depicting the characters of national heroes. It is important to read these books to children and organize their personal library. Parents should pay special attention to the selection of works related to folk oral works from this library .

With the help of speech, a person expresses his thoughts, feelings, and communicates. This is of great importance in the development of the child. When a child is one year old, the ability to learn words is formed. During this period, it is necessary to have more communication with the child . Children ask their parents "Why, what is this, who is this?" They ask a lot of questions like Answering their questions patiently, expanding the child's imagination about the world, the heroes of fairy tales, will be a factor in the acquisition of various knowledge later at school . Children should be introduced to age-appropriate stories, poems, and songs. The child remembers well the sonorous and figurative words in the artistic works of folk

oral creativity, even folk phrases that seem unrelated from the outside, mastering poems also helps the child master the sound and vocabulary of the native language . , is of great importance in understanding its beauty.

School -aged children enrich their speech with new words in the process of getting acquainted with artistic speech. Schools, clubs, palaces of culture, libraries of various forms are of great importance in spreading pedagogical knowledge among the population. "School of Parents " has a special role in this. Parents with different professions will not have a complete picture of pedagogy. They are united by their desire to master the theory of pedagogy and the skills of education . It is expedient to organize "School of parents" in neighborhoods and schools. This "Parenting School" program should include subjects such as pedagogy, psychology, anatomy, physiology, theory and practice of family education. Training should also be held according to a strict schedule. Training in such medical programs should last 1-2 years, training should be conducted by pedagogues, psychologists, physiologists, lawyers, doctors, literary experts, and linguists. Representatives of public organizations should also be involved in training. Course activities provide close support to parents in solving daily educational tasks. In this case, special attention should be paid to inculcating the skills of raising children through the examples of folk oral works in the activities of parents. There are also various ways to increase the effectiveness of family education by means of examples of folk oral creativity.

The fact that family pedagogy lags behind life experiences requires the search for ways to increase its effectiveness. The complex pedagogical processes taking place in the life of society and individual thinking should find scientific solutions in time. Otherwise, it will have a negative impact on the education of young people .

folk oral works promote the activities of people who embody goodness, faith and religion. These works glorify human qualities such as peace, brotherhood, friendship, cooperation, goodness. It condemns any views that threaten peace, are based on fraternity, and cause bloodshed and corruption . There are many examples of family education in the history of pedagogy . Examples of folklore are an

important tool in protecting young people from wrong ideas. To achieve this, you need to do the following:

creation of a single program for instilling in children the good views expressed in the examples of folk oral creativity;

- to increase the knowledge and experience of young parents in the field of raising children by means of examples of folk oral creativity ;

- arming parents with knowledge of family pedagogy, philosophy, literature, history, sociology, social psychology, spirituality, jurisprudence;

- summarizing the positive aspects of folk pedagogy with the help of folklore examples in the family;

- it is necessary to develop a clear, perfect, most important - practical, socio-pedagogical program of folk pedagogy in families and apply it to family education.

It is known that in folklore, our forefathers were intelligent, tried to prevent honest people from falling into the hands of evil forces, and paid special attention to leading children in the family with spirituality, faith, honesty and religion. and in this they effectively used examples of folk art.

Family environment and parental spirituality play an important role in fostering a sense of national pride in young people. Accordingly , the sanctity of the family, the duty of parents and children, thrift, patience, mutual relations, housekeeping, and work education are taught to children through examples of folk art.

Therefore, the duties of the family in raising a sense of national pride in children:

- to create a healthy environment in the family , to take into account the national spirit and lifestyle, to be a role model for children in every way, to form children's feelings of love for their parents and their Motherland, mutual care to provide to be

- to inform their children about the basics of moral knowledge, to ensure that they grow up to be enlightened and spiritual people ;

to create an economic and social environment for children to be spiritually mature and physically healthy ;

- formation of moral and moral aspects of frugality and entrepreneurship in children; oral creativity in the form of folk heroes in the fight against alcoholism and drug addiction .

The use of examples of folklore in family education is of particular importance because parents or grandparents consciously set a specific goal for themselves and strive to achieve this goal, using fairy tales, proverbs, epics, riddles to achieve it. uses effectively. It is necessary to make effective use of educational methods in raising children in the family with the help of examples of folk oral creativity. The following should be taken into account:

The purpose and tasks of education through examples of folk oral creativity.

2. The content of this education.
3. Age characteristics of children.
4. Children's levels of thinking.
5. Individual and personal characteristics of students.
6. Management elements of education, etc.
7. Parents' level of awareness of folk art .
8. Expected results from the educational process.

Thus, bringing up children in the family by means of examples of folk oral creativity is a colorful process that shows unique, unique features. Through examples of folk oral creativity, the child in the family enjoys felicitological ("felicity" in Italian - happiness), economic, aesthetic, communicative, relaxation (restoration of emotional, mental and physical strength, work ability) functions. In order to form a sense of national pride in children , the use of examples of folklore in the family should be carried out with the help of a consistent system and specific methods.

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